

RESULTS OF STUDY OF SWEET PEPPER SAMPLES IN SURKHANDARYA REGION

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ELSEVIER

Karaboev Turgunali Abdujalilovich
Boynazarov Odil Sharofovich

Termiz Agrotechnologies and Innovative Development Institute

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Annotatsiya: The article examines varietal varieties of sweet pepper in the Surkhandarya region. The conclusions are confirmed by practical research.

Kalit so'zlar: Sweet pepper, selection, approbation, counting area, section, grade, standard grade, early maturity, hybrid, productivity.

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РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ОБРАЗЦОВ ПЕРЦА СЛАДКОГО В СУРХАНДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

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Annotatsiya: В статье исследованы сортовые сорта сладкого перца на Сурхандарьинская область. Сделанные выводы подтверждаются практическими исследованиями.

Kalit so'zlar: перец сладкий, селекция, апробация, учётная делянка, делянка, товарность, сорт, стандартный сорт, раннеспелость, гибрид, урожайность.

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СУРХОНДАРЁ ВИЛОЯТИ ШАРОИТИДА ШИРИН ҚАЛАМПИРНИНГ НАВ НАМУНАЛАРИНИ ЎРГАНИШ НАТИЖАЛАРИ

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Annotatsiya: Мақолада Ширин қалампирнинг нав намуналарини Сурхондарё вилояти шароитида ўрганилди. Олинган хулосалар амалий ўрганишлар натижасида исботлаб берилган.

Kalit so'zlar: Ширин қалампир, селекция, апробация, ҳисоб майдони, бўлмача, товарбоп, нав, стандарт нав, эртапишар, дурагай, хосилдорлик.

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Sweet pepper fruit is of particular importance due to its unique taste, good storage on the plant and long-distance shipping, and suitability for processing.

Creation of early, high-yielding and disease-resistant varieties and hybrids of sweet pepper is one of the new directions in our Republic. The creation of such varieties and hybrids will firstly satisfy the demand of the population of our

country for fresh sweet pepper rich in vitamins in early spring, and secondly, it will prevent the decrease of productivity in our republic.

In recent years, the interest of peasant farms and private homestead land owners in this crop, makes it urgent for the breeders of this field to create varieties and hybrids with useful nutrition and high technological quality, resistant to unfavorable factors of the external environment.

Based on this, the selection of high-yielding varieties of sweet pepper, the goal of our research was to create a starting source for obtaining varieties and hybrids with valuable economic characteristics and resistant to external environmental factors.

Research material and method

About 10 samples of varieties brought from Russia and more than 20 varieties and hybrids of the first generation created in our republic served as research material.

Seeds were sown in unheated nurseries on February 12. Seedlings were transplanted to the open field on April 15. Studies “Методические указания по изучению и поддержанию мировой коллекции овощных пасленовых культур (томаты, перцы, баклажаны) (Л.,1977) methodological instruction and “Руководство по апробации овощных культур и кормовых корнеплодов” (М.,1982) was carried out on the basis of Account space 10m², piece three-line. The number of plants in the compartment is 45-60. Planting scheme 70 x30 cm.

Phenological observations were made for the following periods: planting (date), germination of seedlings, transfer of seedlings to the field, flowering (10%, 75%), technical ripening of fruits (10%, 75%), biological ripening (10%, 75%), first and last harvest.

When the fruits ripened, the sweet pepper plant was morphologically characterized according to the following characteristics: plant type, plant height, cm, leafiness, location of the fruit on the plant and others.

The samples of the variety were characterized by important characteristics such as general, marketable yield, average fruit weight, fruit wall thickness, fruit shape, and color.

Research results. Full flowering of plants was recorded on June 1-3, 2021. Technical ripening of fruits was observed on June 15-17.

The period from the germination of the seeds to the biological ripening of the fruits was 118-124 days.

Cultivation work was carried out throughout the growing season. In 50% of the plants, the approval was carried out during the period of biological ripening of the fruits, and the quality of the samples was determined, and the approval

certificate was filled out. As a result, it was determined that the yield of the Nargiza variety is 100% and it was included in the first category.

Study of varieties of sweet pepper.

In 2021, 32 varieties and hybrid samples were studied in comparison with the comparative Nargiza variety.

Seeds were sown in unheated nurseries on February 10.

Seedlings germinated on March 3 and were transplanted to the field on April 12. The technical ripening of fruits was recorded on June 15 in the Tong variety, and on June 24-30 in other varieties. According to the data presented in Table 1, the shortest period of validity was observed in the varieties Tong, Podarok Moldovy, Nargiza, PO 8018, Trufelek krasnyy, Trufelek jeltyy, Knyajich, Kazachok, Super Macroni, LS-14-20, and its duration was 91-110 days. It was 111-119 days in other tested variety samples.

The varieties studied by plant height were divided into two groups: the first group includes varieties with a plant height of 48-56 cm - Dar Tashkenta, Tong, Kazachok, Slastena, Trufelek krasnyy, Trufelek jeltyy, Lekar; the second group includes such varieties as Nargiza, Podarok Moldovy, PO-8018, Superlastochka, A-11-2014, Kaliforniyskoe chudo, Zarya Vostoka, Zumrad, Lastochka, Medok, Victor, Knyajich, Sibiryak, Super Macroni with a plant height of 57-85 cm. It was observed that plants were well leafed in all varieties.

The location of the fruit on the plant is an important feature. For growing in open fields, varieties with fruits located downwards on the plant were considered promising. Among the tested varieties, only the fruits of the Tong variety are located upwards on the plant, and in the rest of the varieties, they are mixed or downwards.

The highest rate of fruit weight was observed in Zumrad and Kaliforniyskoe chudo varieties and it was 135-138 g. These varieties are large-fruited. Very small fruits were observed in Trufelek krasnyy, Trufelek jeltyy and it was 15-16 g.

The fruit weight of the remaining varieties was 39-66 g.

The tested varieties were different in fruit shape: conical, prismatic, cylindrical, square, round. According to the thickness of the fruit wall, the studied varieties were divided into three groups. The first group includes varieties and hybrids with a fruit wall thickness of 2-4 mm: Tong, A-11-2014, Kazachok, Trufelek krasnyy, Trufelek jyoltyy, Medok, Victor, LS-14-20, Dovrps, and they are considered thin-walled.

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